

Chemical Constituents of *Centipeda minima*

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*Centipeda minima*¹ (N.O. Compositae, Hindi—Nakkchikni) recommended for the treatment of toothache, ophthalmia and cold, has been reported to possess an alkaloid, a glycoside traces of saponins² and a bitter amorphous substance ‘‘myriogenin’’³ of unknown constitution. A systematic examination of the plant has been carried out with a view to isolate and identify the active principles.

Dried plant (2.5 Kg) was percolated with methanol (8 litres) and the percolates concentrated to dryness. The dry mass was dissolved in ether and treated with 5% AcOH to extract the alkaloids which could not be isolated after basification. The dark green viscous residue (20 g.) obtained on removal of the ether, was chromatographed over alumina which afforded four crystalline compounds A, B, C and D.

Compound A, m.p. 240–41° [α]_D+55°* C₃₂H₅₂O₂† gave positive tests for triterpenoid and showed the presence of acetyl and isopropenyl functions⁴ in the I.R. spectrum (1739, 1250 and 882 cm⁻¹). The NMR spectrum revealed the presence of a terminal double bond (5.42 τ), an acetoxy group (8.02 τ) and seven methyl groups (8.40–9.20 τ). Deacetylation gave a compound m.p. 199–200° [α]_D+30°, C₃₀H₅₀O which was identified as lupeol through a mixed m.p. determination and preparation of its benzoate m.p. 262° [α]_D+62°, C₃₇H₅₄O₂ and the ketone m.p. 172–73° [α]_D+60°, C₃₀H₄₈O. All these findings except the m.p. of the original compound indicated the identity of A as lupeol acetate (m.p. in literature 216°).

Compound B, m.p. 200° [α]_D+25°, C₃₀H₅₀O giving positive Noller test, was characterised as lupeol through mixed m.p. and preparation of its benzoate m.p. 265° [α]_D+60°, C₃₇H₅₄O₂.

Compound C, m.p. 77–78° was identified as hexacosanol through the preparation of its acetate m.p. 65°, C₂₈H₅₆ O₂ and mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample.

Compound D having a wide melting range was found to be a mixture of β -sitosterol and stigmasterol. The separation was achieved by brominating^{5–6} the acetylated mixture in ether and fractional crystallisation of the product. The less ether-soluble tetrabromo stigmasteryl acetate m.p. 200–202° and more soluble dibromo β -sitosteryl acetate m.p. 120° on debromination and deacetylation gave stigmasterol m.p. 169–70° [α]_D–50° and β -sitosterol m.p. 136° [α]_D–32° respectively.

One of the authors (Y.N.S.) is grateful to Dr. J. S. Tandon for his keen interest and help during the course of this work.

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Received August 22, 1968.

* Rotations were measured as 1% CHCl₃ solution at 35°.

† Satisfactory analytical data on all reported compounds obtained.

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